

VIRCAST

(Virtual Reality CASETool)

A Diagrammatic CASE Tool to Model and Generate Scene Graph based Virtual Reality Environments

David Murphy, Paul Murphy, and Sabin Tabirca

Computer Science Department
University College, Cork, Ireland
d.murphy, p.murphy, s.tabirca@cs.ucc.ie

Abstract. The development of a Virtual Reality (VR) environment differs from the development of regular software applications and systems. Existing software design tools do not cater for these differences. Due to the complexity of the VR development process a design tool that targets these unique requirements is of considerable advantage to VR developers.

This project set out to create an extensible VR Application Programming Interface (API) model and a VR development tool that may be configured for a variety of VR APIs. The concept of an interactive scene graph diagram is very important in the development of VR environments, hence this API model is a scene graph modeller based upon a diagram view rather than a tree view. The tool also contains a source code generator with the ability to generate code for different VR APIs.

Java 3D is a prominent API set developed by Sun for the construction of complex VR environments. Java 3D is comprised of over one hundred different classes each with its own set of methods, and has an extensible architecture enabling support for third-party extensions. The Java 3D API set is used in this project as a test case for the new modeller. The modeller has been found to be intuitive, accurate, and a useful tool for rapid development and teaching VR languages.

1 Introduction

The process of writing source code using a Virtual Reality (VR) application programming interface (API) to develop a VR environment is an error prone and tedious task. The developer must have strong programming skills as well as an understanding of interactive 3D graphics, mathematical tools for the construction and manipulation of geometrical shapes, and an appreciation of the constraints associated with spatial environments and multi-modal user interfaces. This mix of skills is difficult and time-consuming to acquire [1, 2].

The problem is further complicated by the plethora of APIs available to the VR developer. Quite a number of APIs have evolved from academic work and open-source initiatives [3, 4, 5] whilst others are commercial tools, which generally tend to be quite expensive [6, 7, 8, 9]. A common thread between all of the APIs is the manner in

which they represent the elements of a virtual world. The vast majority model the tree view approach to represent the virtual world, which is inherently difficult to use. A far more intuitive approach is one that adopts a diagram view to represent elements of a virtual world – in this approach it is easier for the developer to think spatially instead of hierarchically.

1.1 Project Motivation

The initial goal of this project was to develop a CASE Tool ¹ with a configurable architecture to support a number of the various VR APIs. The tool was designed to address a number of problems in the current VR development process, including:

- There exists no system to constrain the VR developer in the specification of an invalid structure or behaviour.
- The textual nature of source code does not aid in the visualisation of the structure and internal relationships within a VR environment specification.
- The learning curve of a VR API is steep. For instance, the Java 3D API defines over 100 classes, each of which defines several fields and methods.
- There is no standardisation of VR APIs with the consequence that a VR environment being ported from one VR system to another, requires the source code to be rewritten using a different VR API.

1.2 Objectives

With the criteria outlined above (section 1.1) in mind the following development objectives were identified:

1. Develop a *generic* VR API model for scene graph based VR APIs. An API model is a data structure which allows navigation between classes, operations and parameters, and the constraints between them.
2. Develop a scene graph modeller to model the structure and behaviour of a VR environment. The modeller should constrain user interaction to ensure that the corresponding scene graph model is correct and valid.
3. Develop a source code generator to process a scene graph specification and generate a corresponding source code implementation.
4. Develop an application that integrates the VR API model, the scene graph modeller, and the source code generator.

2 Literature Review

In this section, a review of technologies and research that influenced this project will be undertaken. This will take the form of a brief description of each one. The technologies reviewed include: World Toolkit, VRJuggler, CyberToolbox, Alice, DevTools, Java3DTree, Inventor, WorldUp, Obliq 3D and TBAG.

¹ CASE = Computer Assisted Software Engineering

2.1 World Toolkit

World Toolkit (WTK) [6] is a VR library written in C (C++ wrappers are available). To create a virtual world, the developer must write C/C++ code that uses the WorldToolkit API. WTK manages the details of reading sensor input, rendering scene geometry, and loading databases. An application developer only needs to worry about manipulating the simulation and changing the WTK scene graph based on user inputs.

The WTK library is based on object-oriented concepts even though it is written in C and has no inheritance or dynamic binding. WTK functions are ordered in 20 classes. These classes include: Universe (manages all other objects), Geometries, Nodes, Viewpoints, Windows, Lights, Sensors, Paths, and Motion Links. WTK provides functions for collision detection, dynamic geometry, object behaviour, and loading geometry. WTK geometry is based on a scene graph hierarchy. The scene graph specifies how the application is rendered and allows for performance optimization. The scene graph allows features such as object culling, Level of Detail (LOD) switching, and object grouping, to name just a few.

WTK provides functions that allow loading of many database formats into WTK. It includes loaders for many popular data file formats. WTK also allows the user to edit the scene graph by hand if that level of control is needed. Developers can create geometry on the vertex and polygon levels or they can use primitives that WTK provides such as spheres, cones, cylinders, and 3D text. It is of note that when WTK loads in a data file all geometry is put into one node. The data file is not converted into the internal scene graph structure. This means that WTK does not allow the user to manipulate the geometry within their files once loaded. A developer can only manipulate a single node that holds all the geometry.

2.2 VRJuggler

VR Juggler [10] is a VR library written in C++. To create a virtual world, the developer must write C/C++ code that uses the VR Juggler API. VR Juggler gives the developer full access to the graphics API. Therefore, the developer has total freedom when defining the interactions between the user and objects in the virtual world. However, as a consequence, support for interaction in VR Juggler is fairly low-level; the developer must write code to look at the state of the input devices and decide what affect they will have on the environment. There is no event model and no built-in way to associate behaviours with graphic elements. VR Juggler currently supports OpenGL and SGI's Performer software. It has been designed to be extended though, and allows the addition of new graphics supported in a higher level API running on top of VR Juggler. In order to add a new API, the developer only needs to create a new draw manager class and a new application framework class. Since all managers in the library interact with the abstract interface of the draw manager, the rest of the library would be unaffected.

2.3 CyberToolbox

CyberToolbox [11] is a system designed to build the interactive behaviour of a VR scene using a dataflow control model. It features a scene graph node tree, a toolbar containing

the operations which can be performed on each scene graph node and a dataflow diagram editor. The structure of a VR scene is constructed using a scene graph tree which displays scene graph nodes and their parent-child relationship in a hierarchy. The specification of interactive behaviour is achieved by using a dataflow model. The operations which act upon a scene graph node are used as the dataflow nodes in the dataflow model. These dataflow nodes consist of inputs called event in edges and outputs called event out edges. A dataflow node executes when it has data on all its input edges. There are two versions of CyberToolbox, one which is based upon VRML scene graph nodes and the other which is based upon Java 3D scene graph nodes.

2.4 Alice

The Alice [12] system is designed to enable rapid development and prototyping of interactive graphics applications. It has also been designed to provide non-technical users with the ability to write VR programs. Alice has a well designed GUI development which abstracts from the details of 3D graphics and focuses attention on the creation of a VR environment rather than on the technical details of its construction. Alice uses a scripting language to specify the behavioural aspects of the VR environment. Python a high-level, interpreted, object-oriented language is the scripting language used. Alice is designed from the ground up with rapid prototyping in mind. It succeeds at making rapid prototyping easy and powerful. The interpreted scripting language makes it possible to easily test many scenarios very quickly. The development environment is clear and makes developing almost enjoyable. Alice targets non-technical users. Because of this, the product is very simple to learn and use. The scripting language Python) is simple yet powerful. The GUI development environment is clear and easy to use as well.

2.5 DevTools

DevTools [13] is a scene graph viewer and editor developed in part by Sun as a proof of concept Java 3D development tool. It consists of a Swing JTree component which displays a Java3D scene graph hierarchy. It allows for the editing of nodes within the scene graph hierarchy and provides NodeEditors for many common Java 3D objects. It also consists of functionality to help set the bounds and capabilities of scene graph nodes.

2.6 Java3DTree

Java3DTree [14] is scene graph viewer intended to be used as a debugging tool for Java 3D developers. It consists of a Swing JTree component which displays a Java3D scene graph hierarchy and a separate panel to display the properties of the currently selected node. It has the capability to display the scene graph structure and node properties for any given Java 3D scene graph. Java3DTree must be integrated into the source code of the program being debugged when it is being used as a debugging tool. When the program being developed has been compiled and executed, an extra window becomes visible with the Java3DTree component. This allows the developer to see the details of the scene graph while testing or debugging the Java 3D program.

2.7 Inventor

The need for higher level abstractions with low level 3D libraries such as OpenGL has led to the development of 3D Graphics toolkit like Inventor [15]. Inventor implements a hierarchical display list that controls both visual appearance and dynamic behaviour under a single tree structure. The developers of Inventor had hoped that the system would be easier to use than the SGI's native GL library for the creation of 3D direct manipulation applications and even higher level 3D toolkits and to that extent, they were successful.

2.8 WorldUp

Sense8's WorldUp [7] is a commercial application with a CAD-like 3D world editor, complete with scripting language (a variant of Visual Basic), a powerful runtime environment and geometric modelling capabilities. Scripts in WorldUp are attached to geometric objects, and are not centrally located. This has the advantage that code snippets for a single object tend to remain small and tractable, but that inter-object behaviour can be hard to understand and to debug. Fully understanding a pre-authored world in WorldUp can be difficult, as the logic that drives the runtime behaviour is distributed throughout all the objects. In this sense, WorldUp is very similar to traditional 2D GUI builders, in that it depends heavily on an external control model for program control.

2.9 Obliq 3D

Obliq3D [16] is system designed to make 3D scripting easier to use. It uses an interpreted scripting language which is a variant of the Obliq programming language. It has facilities for divorcing the simulation frame rate from the rendering frame rate, and it uses wall-clock time as their primary means for specifying behaviour. It is targeted at the needs of experienced programmers and is both an elegant and functional system.

2.10 TBAG

TBAG [17] is a programming system that uses time and constraints as the primary structuring mechanisms for the specification of behaviour. At TBAG's centre is a constraint engine that drives animations forward by constraining object property values. The system is extremely clean and elegant for those animations that are time-dependent but can be somewhat awkward when dealing with animations that are not easily expressed entirely in time-dependent ways.

As one can see from the aforementioned technologies there does not currently exist a VR specific Integrated Development Environment (IDE) similar to those found in standard software engineering areas. Vircast was designed to address this specific need.

3 Design and Implementation

3.1 VR API Model

The CASE tool is configured for a particular VR API by parsing a VR API specification defined in an external XML file. This specification contains API type definitions for entities such as scene graph nodes, operations, parameters and modeller appearance nodes. The SAX Parser and a custom handler are used to parse and construct the API model. The development of the VR API model also involved the creation of an XML schema for the specification of a valid VR API.

3.2 Scene Graph Modeller

The scene graph modeller uses the node type definitions specified in the VR API model to construct node instances. The modeller is diagram based rather than tree based and allows for the visualisation of scene graph nodes, scene graph components, parent-child relationships and reference relationships. The modeller constrains the construction of the scene graph model to ensure the validity of the specification of the VR environment's structure and behaviours. Several mechanisms were developed for creating constrained relationships between nodes in a scene graph diagram. The visual functionality of the scene graph modeller was implemented by extending the open source JHotDraw drawing framework.

Most VR languages are classed as Scene Description Languages (SDL) and are based upon a scene graph. Common to all SDLs are the basic elements and their relationships.

Scene Graph Nodes The scene graph modeller provides a toolbar containing scene graph node creation tools. As the scene graph nodes are dependent on the target VR API, the instances of these tools need to be dynamically constructed from the VR API specification. The scene graph nodes, which are specified, are typically group nodes, geometry nodes, behaviour nodes, and interpolator nodes. When a developer uses a node creation tool a new instance of the particular node is created in the scene graph.

Parent-Child Relationships The scene graph modeller provides a mechanism for creating parent-child relationships between nodes in a scene graph. When the user attempts to create a parent-child relationship the scene graph modeller verifies that the proposed relationship is a valid one. If the proposed relationship is invalid, the user is constrained from creating the relationship. Figure 1 illustrates this relationship – the solid arrows between the nodes represent the parent child relationship.

Reference Relationships The scene graph modeller also supports the creation of reference relationships. The reference relationship between two scene graph nodes allows for the specification of scene graph node properties, this particular feature is used specifically in Java3D. For instance, the relationship between geometrical nodes and their respective appearance attributes are classed as reference relationships. When the user

Fig. 1. Parent Child Relationship.

attempts to create a reference relationship, the scene graph modeller verifies that the proposed relationship is a valid one and if not the user is prevented from creating the relationship. Figure 2 illustrates this relationship – the dashed arrow between the nodes represents the reference relationship.

Fig. 2. Reference Relationship.

Specifying Behaviour The ability to configure behaviours and behavioural relationships is an important consideration in a tool designed for the development of *interactive* and *dynamic* virtual worlds. Adding behaviour classes to the scene graph is the start of making the virtual scene interactive. The following are the steps involved in setting up a behaviour object in a scene graph diagram using the Java 3D API:

- Add objects of change to the scene graph diagram. This could be as simple as adding a `TransformGroup` with a child node such as a geometric `ColorCube` node.
- Add a `behavior` node to the scene graph diagram and create a reference relationship between it and the objects of change. A behaviour node such as `MouseRotate` object could be added with a `setTransform` reference relationship. See Figure 3 for an illustration of this relationship.
- Specify the scheduling bounds of the `behavior` node by adding a scheduling bounds node and creating a reference relationship between it and the node. Due to inexperience or as an oversight it is possible to omit this step with the consequence that the `Behavior` will never be activated as it has no scheduling bounds and therefore no area in the virtual scene where it will be activated. This can be highly confusing when debugging the virtual scene as it can be difficult to spot why the `behavior` is not working as intended.

- Add read and write capability nodes to the scene graph and create capability relations between them and the object of change. For example, the `TransformGroup` node requires transform read and transform write capabilities to be set before any runtime transformations can take place. Again through inexperience or as an oversight it is possible for a developer to omit this step with the consequence of run time errors occurring when the `Behavior` object attempts to write transform information to the objects of change (see Figure 4).

Fig. 3. Addition of Behaviours to Shapes.

Many approaches for representing the syntax of a target language were examined, however it was an eXtensible Markup Language (XML) approach that was chosen. XML is a set of rules for defining semantic tags that break a document into parts and identify the different parts of the document. It is a meta-markup language that defines a syntax used to define other domain-specific and semantic domains.

In this project an XML description of each scene graph node type is stored in an external XML file and can be used to configure a generalised node type class. An XML-based file format to define a VR API is convenient for developers as it can avoid the frustrating edit/compile/debug cycle when developing a VR API specification. Figure 5 illustrates a generalised node type class configured from a node definition specified in XML.

This external description specifies the operations and properties of a scene graph node type. In XML Fragment 1 (Program 3.1), a simplified definition of the Java3D API `Transform3D` scene graph node has been defined. The definition defines a simplified `Transform3D` node as having three operations each taking one parameter.

Fig. 4. Interactive Behaviours.

Fig. 5. Type and Instance classes defined using an XML definition.

Program 3.1 XML Fragment 1

```

<node name="Transform3D">
  <operation name="setTranslation">
    <param name="translation" type="Vector3d"/>
  </operation>
  <operation name="setScale">
    <param name="scale" type="Vector3d"/>
  </operation>
  <operation name="setRotation">
    <param name="rotation" type="Matrix3d"/>
  </operation>
</node>

```

3.3 SAX Parser

In order to create the node types for a VR API from an XML definition, an XML parser is needed. There are essentially two choices of XML parser: the Document Object Model (DOM) parser, which is a memory based parser that implements a document object model of the XML document, and the SAX parser, which generates events according to tags encountered while sequentially reading from the XML document.

So as to capture and process these events for the VR CASE Tool problem domain, a SAX Handler was implemented that would convert an XML tag definition into an internal object of the VR API model. An important event is when the `startElement` function is called with a "class" tag as a parameter. On this event a new `NodeType` instance is created and is configured by subsequent `startElement` calls. This creates the objects representing the properties of the `NodeType`. For example, in XML Fragment 2 (Program 3.2), three SAX `startElement` processing events will occur followed by three `endElement` processing events, when the fragment is parsed by the SAX parser.

Program 3.2 XML Fragment 2

```
<node name="Transform3D">
  <operation name="setTranslation">
    <param name="translation" type="Vector3d">
      </param>
    </operation>
  </node>
```

When a `startElement` is parsed the handler makes a method call to create a new `NodeType` objects. Subsequent tags will configure the `NodeType` object. Table 1 summarises the matching of a tag with the appropriate SAX event type and the subsequent method call to create objects in the API model.

3.4 Source Code Generator

The implementation of the source code generator consists of several source code templates written using the Velocity Template Language (VTL) [18]. These custom templates produce code targeted for a particular VR API by recursively traversing the scene graph model and mapping node types to VR source code patterns expressed using VTL, the target programming language and the target VR API. The runtime processing of VTL templates required the integration of the open source Velocity Template Engine.

The Vircast source code generator is based on the VTL and uses the Velocity Template Engine. Velocity permits the reference of methods defined in Java code. This means instead of target source code being statically embedded in the source code of the generator, the structure of the target code can be defined externally in a template file. This separation allows the Vircast source generator to be flexibly configured and externally modified. The following is the procedure used to develop source code templates for a particular target scene graph based VR API.

Tag	Event Type	Method Call	Target Class	Description
<node>	StartElement	createNodeType	NodeType	create new NodeType
<operation>	StartElement	createOperationType	OperationType	create new OperationType
<param>	StartElement	createParameterType	ParameterType	create new ParameterType
</param>	EndElement	addParameterType	OperationType	adds the new ParameterType to OperationType
</operation>	EndElement	addOperationType	NodeType	adds the new ParameterType to OperationType
</node>	EndElement	addNodeType	API	adds the new ParameterType to OperationType

Table 1. XML Tag to SAX Event Type to Method Call Table

- Identify common patterns in the source code of programs using the VR API. For instance, a common pattern is the way in which a scene graph is constructed. It takes the form of several function definitions which create a group node, add child nodes to the group node and returns the newly created group node.
- Parameterize these patterns using the Velocity Template Language References. VTL provides several constructs for preparing a pattern to use parameters. Access to the scene graph model is obtained via a context object provided by the source code generator.
- Store these patterns in an external text format so they can load into the Velocity Template Engine.

4 Conclusions

Vircast as a development tool is quite unique in that there are very few tools available designed specifically to assist in VR development, and even fewer that are based upon CASE methodologies.

4.1 Architecture

The architecture of the implemented solution has proven to be very flexible. At the end of the development process, several different XML VR API specifications were created and used to configure the CASE tool. Each XML file contained different permutations of scene graph nodes and different sets of operations. The VR Case tool was correctly configured for each of these specifications, which demonstrated the CASE tool's ability to be configured for a variety of VR APIs.

4.2 Rapid Development

The development of sample scene graph diagrams proved to be more intuitive than writing corresponding source code. Specification is achieved by the visual connection of nodes to form relationships and as a result of the constraints enforced by the scene graph modeller, the relationships are always valid. The ability to rapidly produce source code allows the developer to experiment and quickly test ideas and concepts.

4.3 Informative Diagrams

The information conveyed by a scene graph diagram has proven to be more visually informative than the scene graph tree employed by other 3D/VR tools. An important feature is the ability of the scene graph diagram to model reference relationships between nodes. For instance, the most important relationship that a scene graph node has may not be its parent-child relationship, but its reference relationship with another node.

An issue that arose when users started using the tool is that the developer needs to have an understanding of rudimentary scene graph theory and a basic knowledge of the nodes within the target VR API so as to commence creating a VR scene.

Vircast is not intended for use by novices, however, as the development of Vircast progressed it became clear how the tool could be further enhanced to cater for the needs of novices. Node components could be created that hide the complexity of 3D graphics theory. For instance, instead of specifying a translation to move an object, the 3D graphics theory of matrix transformations could be hidden and abstracted away using a method call called "move" and specify the number and type of units the object is to be moved by. This is the approach adopted in the Alice research project [12]. Through their research they found ways to further abstract away from the scene graph concept. In fact the scene graph is cleverly hidden from the developer. For example, instead of using 3D graphics methods such as translate, rotate and scale, alternative mechanisms are used to accomplish the same tasks using familiar concepts such as move, turn and resize.

4.4 Learning

Vircast has also proven to be a useful tool for learning a VR API. The language-specific constraints enforced by Vircast ensure the developer quickly learns the valid relationships between nodes and other elements in the target language. It is also valuable in assisting the developer in becoming familiar with the language-specific nuances relating to scene construction. The authors have also gathered anecdotal information that supports the use of Vircast as a teaching tool in VR development.

References

- [1] William R. Sherman and Alan B. Craig. *Understanding Virtual Reality: Interface, Application, And Design*. Morgan Kaufmann, San Francisco, CA, 2003.
- [2] Richard Brice. *Multimedia and Virtual Reality Engineering*. Newnes, Oxford, 1997.
- [3] SICS. Distributed interactive virtual environment (dive). <http://www.sics.se/dive/>, March 2003.
- [4] Web3D. Virtual reality modeling language. <http://www.web3d.org/WorkingGroups/vrml-conf/index.html>, March 2003.
- [5] Web3D. extensible 3d. <http://www.web3d.org/fsx3d.htm>, March 2003.
- [6] Sense8 Corporation. Worldtoolkit release 8: Technical overview. <http://www.sense8.com>, September 2002.
- [7] Sense8 Corporation. Worldup: Technical overview. <http://www.sense8.com>, September 2002.
- [8] Blaxxun Ltd. Blaxxun virtual worlds platform 5. <http://www.blaxxun.com/solutions/applications/virtualworlds/index.shtml>, 2003.
- [9] Sony. Community place. <http://vs.sony.co.jp>, 2002.
- [10] Allen Bierbaum and Christopher Just. Software tools for virtual reality application development. In *The Proceedings of SIGGRAPH*, 1998.
- [11] S. Konno. Cybertoolbox. <http://www.cybergarage.org/>, 2002.
- [12] et al R. Pausch. A brief architectural overview of alice, a rapid prototyping system for virtual reality. *IEEE Computer Graphics and Applications*, May 1995.
- [13] Sun Microsystems. Devtools. <http://java.sun.com/products/java-media/3D/demos/downloads/>, September 2002.

- [14] Tornado Labs. J3dtree. <http://www.tornadolabs.com/News/J3dTreeHome/>, September 2002.
- [15] Paul Strauss and Rick Carey. An object-oriented 3d graphics toolkit. In *Proceedings of 92 ACM SIGGRAPH*, pages 341–349. ACM SIGGRAPH, 1992.
- [16] Mark Najork. Obiq-3d tutorial and reference manual. Technical Report 129, Digital Equipment Corporation, Systems Research Center, 1994.
- [17] Conal Elliot, Greg Schecter, Ricky Yeung, and Salim Abi-Ezzi. Tbag: A high-level framework for interactive animated 3d graphics applications. In *The Proceedings of ACM SIGGRAPH*, 1994.
- [18] Jakarta. Apache jakarta project: Velocity template engine. URL, September 2002. <http://jakarta.apache.org/velocity/>.